

**METHODOLOGY FOR THE IMPROVEMENT OF FUTURE
TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL
ENVIRONMENT INFORMING THEIR METHODOLOGICAL
COMPETENCE**

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***Annotation:** This article focuses on the systematic directions of methodological competence of future technological education teachers in the informational educational environment. The place of information communication is incomparable for each growing young generation to fully respond to the demands of the time. Taking this into account, special attention was paid to some aspects of the educational environment. Necessary recommendations and instructions for the methodical competence of future teachers of technological education have been given.*

***Key words:** Informed education, methodology, methodological competence, pedagogy, professional skill, qualification.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the main tasks of the educational process is to bring up the young generation who are being formed as creators of the fundamental reforms implemented in our republic, to acquire knowledge at the level of modern requirements, to mature as individuals, to learn the secrets of professions and to

solve daily life tasks. is happening.

Organization of the educational process based on the requirements of the times, including the introduction of information and communication technologies in the higher education system, special attention is paid to the training of highly qualified personnel. As a result of the reforms of the last ten years, the necessary political-legal, socio-economic and scientific-educational foundations for the establishment of a new Uzbekistan were created in our country. Based on the in-depth analysis of complex global processes and the results of our country's progress, in the following years, based on the principle of "For human dignity", we will further increase the well-being of our people, transform economic sectors and rapidly develop entrepreneurship, unconditionally ensure human rights and interests, and In order to determine the priority directions of reforms aimed at forming an active civil society, as a result of public discussion, the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, developed on the basis of the principle "From the strategy of actions to the strategy of development" and called it "Attention to people and In accordance with the state program for the implementation" of "quality education" in seven priority directions, the following directions occupy a key place:

- ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level;
- approach to universal problems based on national interests [1-2].

Based on this, it is not an exaggeration to say that not only educators, but all of us are responsible for the development of each growing young generation into a fully mature and potential person. In order to achieve the result we expect, it would be appropriate if future teachers of technological education increase, strengthen, develop their knowledge, skills and qualifications, and engage more in their work. The 21st century is the age of information technologies, which is becoming important for the future and tomorrow of every young generation. The development of information communications is progressing all over the world. One of today's tools is the application of information technology, which is rapidly entering the

practice of all fields, into the process of higher education. The global information network can provide information in any field, regardless of the size and speed, for receiving it in the desired amount. It cannot be denied that the role and influence of information technologies in the development of a well-rounded person, his independent choice of profession and professional self-formation, and the development of professional skills are increasing. Using computers and information technologies, it creates new opportunities in the development of creative thinking of future teachers of technological education in the field of education and educational activities. Information technologies allow to combine education with life in the process of implementation.

There will be an opportunity to closely connect education with future professional activity. Teaching the treasure of science accumulated over the years to today's young future generation, training them to become mature specialists who meet world standards with the help of advanced and modern pedagogical technology and information systems in the world has become one of the main tasks of today's era. One of the important requirements of the present day is the completeness of the educational process is to conduct using computer networks [3].

It is necessary for republican pedagogues to strengthen comprehensive structural reforms in the education system by mastering advanced pedagogical technologies and applying them to the educational process. For this, it is necessary to train our pedagogues in the technological approach to the educational process, which, in addition to the use of pedagogical technologies, will enrich it with the culture, traditions and experience of Uzbekistan.

Analysis of the literature. It consists in using the most appropriate educational technology for teaching science. Also, for more effective teaching, elements of other technologies, such as game technology and group teaching technology, should be included in the pedagogical process. In order to successfully study science, it is necessary to combine the reproductive activity of students with the activation of their independent search activity, development of spatial thinking, creative professional thinking. In the process of teaching, many researchers and Uzbek scientists are conducting research, these researches are mainly aimed at studying and increasing the social needs of the educational process, improving the methodological competence of future technological education teachers.

The future teacher of technological education must now not only perform his functional duties well, but also be able to design various processes, accept solutions and perform creative work. There is a real need for the use of informational education, one of the educational technologies, in technological training

sessions, which requires continuous work on the introduction of multimedia tools into the system. Because multimedia opens the way to non-traditional sources of information, new forms and teaching methods for students of education and upbringing. In multimedia programs, information is transmitted using three means - graphics, audio and video. With the help of computer graphics, there is an opportunity to maximally implement the aesthetic laws of the structure of the form. This combines the elements of the representation of the object with the real world in technological education. This category of visualization is classified by its schematic and encrypted mental image.

Research methodology. Improving the methodological competence of future teachers of technological education begins in the process of obtaining professional knowledge in higher educational institutions. In the curriculum and science programs of higher educational institutions, future technological education should teach teachers the secrets of the profession they are interested in, provide scientific knowledge, provide information about the chosen profession and skills generation is meant [4].

Seminars, practical and laboratory trainings in subjects during the educational process allow not only to strengthen theoretical knowledge and turn them into skills, but also to apply them in the practical work process. Such training instills a sense of confidence that the chosen profession is the right one. It is an urgent issue of today to organize the education of the young generation growing up in our country's education system based on national ideas and requirements so that it meets the prospects of society's development and world standards. Fundamental reform of the educational system, cleaning it from the remnants of the past and developed democratic countries raising the level, training highly qualified personnel who meet high moral and ethical requirements for the development of society is the general task of the employees of the educational system.

In order to improve the methodological competence of future teachers of technological education, it is necessary to pay attention to the development of observability. In order to acquire socio-perceptive competence in the process of pedagogical activity and communication, the specialist should train himself with humane, social-reflexive, knowledge and skills, positive professional "I"- image and some personal qualities. it is desirable to engage [5].

In order to improve the methodological competence of future teachers of technological education in an informational educational environment, it is necessary to check their ability to use computer technologies effectively and give them insights accordingly. The use of visual aids, electronic boards and interesting materials related to the subject will certainly help to achieve the expected result.

The knowledge, skills and abilities of the student are important for the development of future technological education teachers. Certain qualities of a person are formed through a set of practical educational activities. It is necessary that these works should be clearly multifaceted, and at the same time, they should be carried out on the basis of mental, physical, moral, aesthetic and labor education. A holistic educational approach requires a systematic attitude and management of the educator. Management can be successful only if external and internal factors involved in the educational process and their interaction are taken into account. In acquiring pedagogical skills, acquiring theoretical and practical knowledge of the profession, constant communication with the pedagogical team gives positive results. Of course, in such an environment, exchanging opinions, comparing personal opinions with the opinions expressed by others, making sure that they are correct and truthful, increasing self-confidence, enriching existing knowledge, and correcting mistakes and shortcomings. creates an opportunity to engage more in learning and shallow knowledge. “A teacher should regularly study science. Otherwise, it will look like a dead tree and a stone. Just as a dry tree and a stone cannot bear fruit, no results can be expected from such teachers in the future” [6].

Based on the pedagogical experiences of countries that are leaders in the development of information and communication technologies in the world, it is important to widely apply modern information and communication technologies to the educational process and to raise the quality of education to a new level, to prepare future teachers for professional activities. From this point of view, it is necessary to form pedagogical professional competence in accordance with the requirements of the labor market through the effective use of elearning resources in the preparation of teaching students in higher education institutions for professional activities at the level of international standards [7].

Conclusions and suggestions. In short, if multimedia lessons are used in the educational process, the future technological education teacher will have to fulfill certain qualification requirements. As a result, the future technological education teacher's pedagogical competence will develop, his health and pedagogical skills will increase, the student's level of knowledge and the quality of training will rise to a higher level. This creates an opportunity to organize and manage the educational process, to periodically update the educational content [8-13]. Therefore, it is important to justify the criteria for evaluating the possession of certain qualities in future teachers of technological education.

Adabiyotlar ro'yxati. References

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 28-yanvardagi “2022-2026-yillarga

mo'ljallangan yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risida" gi PF-60-sonli farmoni.
Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 "On the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026".

2. SH.M.Mirziyoyev. "Erkin va farovon, demokratik O'zbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz". O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti lavozimiga kirishish tantanali marosimiga bag'ishlangan Oliy Majlis Palatalarining qo'shma majlisidagi nutq -Toshkent: "O'zbekiston", 2016-yil.

Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. "Free and prosperous, democratic country of Uzbekistan together we will build". Speech at the joint session of the Chambers of the Oliy Majlis dedicated to the inauguration ceremony of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", 2016.

3. O.A.Qo'ysinov "Kompetentli yondashuv asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy pedagogik ijodkorligini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari" Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha doktorlik (DSc) diss. – Toshkent, 2019-yil 47-bet.

O.A.Koysynov "Technologies for the development of professional pedagogical creativity of future teachers based on a competent approach" Doctorate in Pedagogical Sciences (DSc) diss. - Tashkent, page 47 of 2019.

4. M.K.Shomirzayev Combined In Technology Courses Use Of Technologies //The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations. 2021. – T. №05.– P. 389- 396 betlar.

M.K.Shomirzayev Combined In Technology Courses Use Of Technologies //The American Journal of Social Science and Educational Innovations. 2021. - T. no. 05. – P. 389-396 pages.

5.B.E.Qodirov "Elektron axborot ta'lim muhitida o'quvchilarning hunarmandchilikka oid tayanch kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi". Diss. p.f.f.d. (PhD) – Termiz: 2021-yil 142-bet.

B.E.Kadirov "Methodology of development of basic skills of students in the electronic information education environment". Diss. p.f.f.d. (PhD) – Termiz: 2021 page 142.

6. U.SH.Begimqulov "Pedagogik ta'limda zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarini joriy etishning ilmiy nazariy asoslari". - T:Fan 2007-yil 157-bet.

U.S.Begimkulov "Scientific theoretical foundations of introduction of modern information

technologies in pedagogical education”. - T:Fan 2007 page 157.

7.N.A.Muslimov, O.A.Qo‘ysinov, Sh.Abduraxmonov, Q.M.Abdullaeva, N.S. Gaipova, “Bo‘lajak kasb ta’limi o‘qituvchilarining metodik kompetentligini shakllantirish texnologiyalari”. Metodik qo‘llanma. – T.: 2014 yil. 90-95-betlar.

N.A.Muslimov, O.A.Koysinov, Sh.Abdurakhmanov, Q.M.Abdullaeva, N.S.Gaipova, “Technologies of formation of methodical competence of future vocational education teachers”. Methodical manual. - T.: 2014. Pages 90-95.

8. Nosirov, N. (2023). Bo‘lajak texnologiya fani o‘qituvchilarining metodik kompetentligini rivojlantirish jarayonini takomillashtirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari. Farg‘ona davlat universiteti, (1), 207-207.

Nosirov, N. (2023). Pedagogical conditions for improving the process of developing methodical competence of future technology teachers. Fergana State University, (1), 207-207.

9. Nosirov, N. V., & Ismoilova, S. S. (2024). RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING TA’LIM SOHASIDA QO‘LLANILISHI. Innovations in Science and Technologies, 1(3), 175-179.

Nosirov, N. V., & Ismailova, S. S. (2024). USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION. Innovations in Science and Technologies, 1(3), 175-179.

10.Valijonovich, N. N. (2023, July). EDUCATION OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS FORMING THE SKILLS OF USING TECHNOLOGIES. In International Scientific and Current Research Conferences (pp. 13-16).

Valijonovich, N. N. (2023, July). EDUCATION OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS FORMING THE SKILLS OF USING TECHNOLOGIES. In International Scientific and Current Research Conferences (pp. 13-16).

11.N.V.Nosirov “Bo‘lajak texnologiya fani o‘qituvchilarini metodik kompetentligini rivojlantirish mezonlari” “Criteria for the Development of Methodological Competence of Future Teachers of Technology” International Journal on Integrated Education. Research parks publishing Indonesia. In Vol.6 No r (2023).

N.V. Nosirov “Criteria for the Development of Methodological Competence of Future Teachers of Technology” “Criteria for the Development of Methodological Competence of Future Teachers

of Technology” International Journal on Integrated Education. Research Parks Publishing Indonesia. In Vol. 6 No. r (2023).

12. N.V.Nosirov “Bo‘lajak texnologiya fani o‘qituvchilarida kasbiy va metodik kompetentlikni shakllantirishda integratsion jarayondan foydalanish”. “Mug‘allem hem uzluksiz bilimlendio” Ilmiy jurnali. Nukus. №5/2. 2022-yil.129-134-betlar.

N.V. Nosirov “Using the integration process in the formation of professional and methodical competence of future technology teachers”.“Teacher and continuous education” Scientific magazine. Defect. No. 5/2. 2022. Pages 129-134.

13.N.V.Nosirov “Bo‘lajak texnologiya fani o‘qituvchilarini metodik kompetentligini takomillashtirishning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari”. “NamDU ilmiy xabarlar” Ilmiy jurnali. Namangan 11-son. 2022-yil 636-641-betlar.

N.V. Nosirov “Pedagogical and psychological foundations of improving the methodological competence of future technology teachers”. “Scientific news of NamSU” scientific magazine. Namangan No. 11. 2022 pp. 636-641.